

APPLYING COMMUNITY UNDERSTANDING TO AID IN THE PRESERVATION OF CONVENTIONAL ALLEGIANCES

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ABSTRACT

According to this research, the lingual unit is used to express local wisdom and preserve culturally significant values by explaining how its forms and functions are used. Petatah-petitih must be re-disclosed in order for the information it contains to be valid throughout time and not just during the lifetime of Sunan Gunung Jati. Recognizing and putting into practice the high cultural values helps to build up the character of the next generation. Studies of cultural values petatah-petitih Sunan Gunung Jati use anthropological theoretical characters to study linguistic units. The research paradigm used in this study is qualitative. The findings revealed that words, phrases, sentences, and meanings are all forms of lingual units that express local wisdom. Second, the lingual unit that expresses local wisdom has three functions: teachings about life outlook, advice, and prohibition.

Keywords: Traditions and customs, linguistics, environmental protection

INTRODUCTION

Language can describe the effects of a community's cultural traditions in the same way that language is shaped by culture. The language will represent the diversity and richness of the culture. Aside from that, language is the primary means of transmitting and transmitting cultural history. Language is an important part of society since it influences our thinking (Sibarani, 2004). The society of a culture has a distinct style of thinking, which is mirrored in the language. A language's concrete form might be used to identify it. Linguistic units and lingual units are names for tangible forms of language. Lingual units are units that have meaning, such as words and phrases (Kridalaksana, 2001). Whorf's language, according to Sapir-theory, has an impact on both culture and the speaker's psyche. That is, if one nation differs from another in terms of culture, it must also differ in terms of thought. Thinking cannot be transferred from one language to another, according to Wierzbica (1992), who agrees with Sapir-Worf, because its formulation is so reliant on the language. As a result, language functions as both a tool for thinking and a bridge between different civilizations.

This indicates that the behaviour of an ethnic group is intrinsically related to the language in which they communicate. If a group's style of thinking can be represented through language, culture may be expressed through it as well.

When people learn culture, they become part of a larger system that includes ideas, actions, and results of human work. It's clear from this description that language and culture go hand in hand. Language and culture are intertwined in human existence, influencing one another, complementing one another, and coexisting. To summarise, the process of understanding text involves two stages: analysing the text's linguistic form and searching for cultural significance and values. Language must be learned in relation to culture in order to learn culture and vice versa is at the heart of this relationship (Sibarani, 2004).

When one or more elements of culture are prominent, language and text can transmit and grasp the link between them (Sibarani, 2004). The phrase is a linguistic form that expresses meaning and function in terms of cultural values.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Anthropolinguistics is a field of linguistics that studies how languages have evolved over time, how people communicate in different environments, how kinship systems function, and other cultural patterns within a tribe's culture. Because of the importance of language in understanding cultural terms, talking with others, and communicating with people from various cultures, language and culture are connected in anthropolinguistics (Sibarani, 2004).

To summarise, anthropolinguistic research focuses on three primary areas: culture, language, and other spheres of life. As a result, they are an interdisciplinary topic of research that straddles the divide between linguistics and anthropology. Linguistics and anthropology examine the three areas in the same context. There are two theoretical frameworks: one is based on linguistic studies, while the other is based on human life studies. It's vital to remember that anthropolinguistics encompasses both the study of language and culture within an anthropological framework and the study of human life in general within an anthropological-linguistic framework.

The text is organised according to the investigation's goals using the Van Dijk principle. Van Dijk (1985) mentions three frameworks when it comes to text structure: macro, super, and micro (in that order). By concentrating on the topic or theme that the book discusses in depth, the macro structure of the text can be deduced. The superstructure, also known as the flow structure, is the collection of literary pieces that join together to form a coherent whole in a text. Microstructure refers to the structure of individual words within a text in theoretical linguistics. Theoretical phonology, which deals with the structure of words and sentences at the individual word and sentence level, is one of the numerous fields of linguistic theory.

You'll need to be familiar with the complexities of phonemic and phonetic studies if you want to explore the microstructures of texts. You'll need to know how to use phrases, clauses, and sentences as well. Text microstructure studies can be done in parallel, although different degrees of analysis can be used based on the text's features. The emphasis is on phonology and morphology in pantun texts, while syntax and discourse are the centre of mythological tales. Cultural studies place a high value on context. Beyond the co-texts, context heavily influences the meaning of a text's lingual elements. Text can serve a variety of purposes depending on the context in which it is used.

LOCAL KNOWLEDGE

The ability of a country to absorb and even cultivate cultures from other countries is determined by its cultural personality. Local wisdom is the term for this (Wibowo, 2015: 17). As a result, despite these people's various identities and personalities, their values stay consistent. Using local wisdom is one technique to nurture culture while also defending against invading civilizations. Istiawatin (2016) defines local wisdom as people's reactions to changes in their physical and cultural environments. When we talk about local wisdom, we're referring to well-founded, wise, and worthwhile thoughts.

Local wisdom, according to Ratna (2011), is an existent cultural bond that is based on the fact that it exists in the first place. The experts who contributed to this page unanimously agree that "local wisdom" refers to concepts that originate and develop through time. According to Haryanto (2014), local wisdom manifests itself in religious concord manifested in culturally grounded social practises. Honesty, respect, and civility, as well as ingenuity, hard effort, and unwavering leadership, are all admirable values. Local knowledge can be found in folklore, wise sayings, and proverbs (parikan, paribasan, bebasan and saloka). Local wisdom can come in two forms: oral and written.

The Wording of the Sentence

This traditional expression is also known by different titles, such as wise men and wise ladies. The phrase has a figurative sense in ordinary speech, referring to how a person or society acts in regular events. According to Dundes and Russell (in Danandjaja, 2002), traditional idioms are brief sentences extracted from long experiences. As a result, traditional proverbs frequently include wise comments from wise people who have gone through a variety of life events. Traditional expression benefits people both individually and collectively.

According to Simanjuntak (1984), traditional sentences are brief sentences utilised by the general people. The term can be interpreted as communicating a message, giving guidance, or providing figurative responses. Traditional expressions have religious and customary values. Traditionally, those in the community who are well-known for employing the traditional expression pass it down from generation to generation. The ancient term is used as a sort of social control since it contains inferred meaning. Rules, reprimands, and

restrictions on certain activities can all be conveyed through expressions. Oral and cultural traditions rely heavily on folk ways of expressing oneself (Sulistiyorini & Andalas, 2017). To express ideas, petitions, verses, recommendations, and figures of speech are used (Karim, 2015). Traditional expressions have liberated the great principles they once held.

METHOD

To obtain first-hand information, the entire study incorporates qualitative research methods (Moleong, 2011). This research takes an anthropolinguistic approach to language, which examines it from a cultural perspective. Anthropolinguistics is a multidisciplinary field of research (Sibarani, 2004). This study relies on qualitative data. The type of information you're looking for is described here.

It is important to transcribe all of the information into different expression forms, classify them, and analyse the linguistic features of all of the shapes in petatah-petitih before any data reduction can take place. Before presenting the data, analyse the meaning inherent in phrases to exhibit data and create links between phenomena. The third and final step is to come to a conclusion and double-check everything. Conclusions are reached through a multi-step procedure that begins with data collection and finishes with data verification. The validity of the data is influenced by sources, methodologies, and theories (Sutopo, 2006).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Local knowledge is communicated in words, phrases, and sentences to maintain the life of culturally noble values. Language has the ability to safeguard cultural values by assisting in their survival. This is consistent with Sibarani's (2004: 46) statement that language is a cultural construct intimately related to the mental process. The language will be diverse and rich in order to reflect the culture's diversity. Language is not only an important aspect of culture, but also a major means of cultural transmission and evolution. In the next paragraphs, the linguistic forms will be further explained.

Word

A word is formed when many syllables unite to form a phrase (Ramlan, 2009). Words can be used to express how members of a speech community feel and think. This linguistic unit is used by the community to express local wisdom and to preserve noble qualities in expressions.

Duwehna "meaningful actions"

As a result of morphological processes, notably affixation, the word has become highly complex. To determine an affix's position, utilise the affix position relation. Configuration is created when the creation process culminates in a single grammatical meaning. Prefixes and suffixes, for example, do not have lexical meanings, according to Mulyono (2013). When there are affixes in a phrase, the basic form is always added to make complicated words.

Respect is required not only from fellow Muslims, but also from ancestors, parents, scientists, and cultural legacy. The existence of ancestors can provide historical insights into the past as well as lessons for the future. This is the same as historical research. The characters' backstories and numerous historical events serve two purposes: inspiration and recreation. History can bring new ideas and solutions to critical societal concerns in addition to providing entertainment in the form of literary works. History, like the past, is used as a teaching and learning tool. Understanding the past as a series of life events will help you obtain insight and wisdom for a sustainable future.

Islam establishes standards for judging good and poor activities, particularly in terms of how they are carried out. Someone who has noble intentions but goes about it the wrong way, doing a horrific deed as a result. These petitions demonstrate a flagrant disregard for the law. In order to prevent displaying this bad trait, one must be modest and not feel superior to others. Bad traits must be avoided at all costs if a person's well-being is to be preserved.

Because being hostile can be a source of division, the word "Angadohna" means "prevent hostility or quarrelling," the message included in these petitions is one of avoiding and avoiding enmity. These petath-petitih place a high emphasis on character, which manifests itself in the form of tolerance. You show others that you care about them and that you have a kind heart by staying out of each other's way. Helping and encouraging others is a desirable character trait to have.

"Duwehna" means "excellent qualities in the data" in Petatah-petitih. The deeper meaning of these petitih is to be wary by nature. People should be able to show off their charitable side when they interact and communicate. These petitih act as visual representations of piety in action. A caring and giving personality acts as a barrier between you and the rest of society. With a liberal perspective, mental health partnerships can be properly nourished.

CONCLUSIONS

Following the analysis of these figures, two conclusions may be drawn. First, the linguistic units employed in Cirebon society to express local wisdom, these included linguistic units of words, phrases, and sentences. second, the instructional activity, advise or commands are all language units employed by the Cirebon speech group to represent local wisdom in regard to the conservation of cultural heritage values.

The Individuals must value regional wisdom as a valuable cultural asset. Apart from that, the community must safeguard and retain its distinct cultures. The flea's wisdom is one

of Cirebon's indigenous knowledge. To preserve the oral legacy, the speech community employs these lingual units. As a result, by adding knowledge into education, the community must sustain and preserve its wisdom.

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